

Pyrilium Salts and *spiro*-Dipyrans. Part I. Condensation Products from *o*-Hydroxy-aldehydes and α -Alkylated β -ketonic Esters.

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Synthesis of anhydropyranol or pyrylium salts have been investigated by a large number of investigators (Wagner and Bülow, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 1195; Dilthey, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1904, 70, 275; 1916, 94, 72; Schneider and Rors, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2775). The methods depend chiefly on the use (i) of a phenol and a substance containing the group, CHO·CH₂·CO and (ii) of an *o*-hydroxy aldehyde and a substance containing the group ·CH₂·CO—. The pyrylium salt is isolated in the form of a ferric or perchloric acid salt. The following examples exhibit the relations between the two methods:

Up till now, *o*-hydroxy-aldehydes have not been condensed with α -alkylated β -ketonic esters, although β -ketonic esters, *e.g.*, aceto- and benzoyl-acetic esters have been condensed with *o*-hydroxy aldehydes to coumarone derivatives (Kostanecki, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1148) using piperidine as the condensing agent. In the present communication, which is of a preliminary character, the author has described the behaviour of *o*-hydroxy-aldehydes towards α -alkylated β -ketonic esters in presence of gaseous hydrochloric acid. It has been found that those ketonic esters containing only one reactive hydrogen atom in the alpha position readily react with the aldehydes to yield highly coloured benzopyrylium salts. In each case two molecules of the aldehyde and one of the ester yield a 3-alkyl-2-(*o*-hydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium salt. An unsuccessful attempt was made by the author to prepare a pyrylium compound from acetoacetic ester and salicylaldehyde in presence of hydrochloric acid.

The reaction product, which had an intensive red colour, did not respond to the usual properties of pyrylium salts or of coumarones.

As to the mechanism of the reaction in the formation of pyrylium salts, it is presumed that the first phase of the condensation involves the elimination of the carbethoxy group and the formation of a primary 2:3-dialkylbenzopyrylium salt. The second phase in the condensation depends on the presence of a reactive 2-methyl group (Plancher, *Gazzetta*, 1898, 28, 417; Dilthey, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 1012; Mills, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2724) which condenses with the second molecule of the aldehyde producing 3-alkyl-2-(*o*-hydroxy styryl)-benzopyrylium salt. The following example explains the reaction.

The above explanation for the mechanism finds support from the following observations:—

(i) The pyrylium salt derived from α -methylacetoacetic ester and salicylaldehyde is identical with that prepared from salicylaldehyde and the 2:3-dimethylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride of Decker (*Annalen*, 1909, 364, 37). (ii) 2-Phenyl-3-methylbenzopyrylium perchlorate obtained from salicylaldehyde and propiophenone by Decker's method is identical with that derived from salicylaldehyde and α -methylbenzoylacetic ester. The close resemblance between the two synthetic methods is thus represented:—

By hydrolytic decomposition of the *o*-hydroxystyryl benzopyrylium salts, the pseudo bases, 2-hydroxy-2-(*o*-hydroxystyryl)- α -chromanes could not be isolated; the alcoholic and phenolic hydroxyl

groups react with the elimination of a molecule of water and formation of *spiro*-dipyrans (Decker, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 2997; *Annalen*, 1908, **364**, 87). The *spiro*-dipyrans, which are colourless, are converted by strong acids into the highly coloured hydroxystyryl benzopyrylium salts. The cycle of changes is represented below.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3-Methyl-2-(o-hydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium chloride.

A mixture of salicylaldehyde (2 mols.) and α -methylacetoacetic ester (1 mol.) was diluted with dry ether and dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed into the ethereal solution, cooled by ice, for 2 to 3 hours. The deep coloured crystals that separated were filtered, washed with ether and dried in a vacuum. It was obtained in deep red needles having a coppery lustre, m.p. 200°. (Found: C, 72.58; H, 5.26. C₁₈H₁₄O₂Cl requires C, 72.86 and H, 5.08 per cent.)

3-Methyl-2-(o-hydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium ferric chloride.—

(a) The pyrylium chloride was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and to this was added an acetic acid solution of ferric chloride. The ferric salt separated as a red flocculent precipitate which, when crystallised from acetic acid, was obtained in red needles, m.p. 180°.

(b) 2:3-Dimethylbenzopyrylium ferric chloride (Decker, *loc. cit.*) was heated with salicylaldehyde in acetic acid solution. On cooling and allowing to stand, the ferric salt separated in long needles; it was washed with ether and dried, m.p. 180°. (Found: C, 47.17; H, 3.51. C₁₈H₁₄O₂FeCl₄ requires C, 46.85; H, 3.25 per cent.)

3-Methyl-2-(o-hydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium perchlorate was obtained by adding perchloric acid to the pyrylium chloride dissolved in acetic acid. The deep red crystals that separated were filtered, washed with acetic acid and then with ether, m.p. 244°. (Found: C, 59.69; H, 4.35. C₁₈H₁₄O₂Cl requires C, 59.57; H, 4.19 per cent.)

3-Methyl-spiro-dibenzopyran.

The decomposition of the above ferric salt was effected in the following way. The salt was intimately mixed with anhydrous sodium acetate and the mixture was suspended

in ether to which strong ammonia solution was added drop by drop. The mixture was frequently shaken and the addition of ammonia was continued till the colour of the ferric salt disappeared. The reaction product, which remained in solution, was filtered from ferric hydroxide and was obtained in crystals on the evaporation of the ether. Purified by crystallisation from petroleum ether, it was obtained in white needles, m.p. 80°. (Found: C, 81.78; H, 5.91. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 82.01; H, 5.70 per cent.)

It is soluble in alcohol, benzene and ether; difficultly soluble in petroleum ether. From the colourless solution the pyrylium compound is precipitated as the ferric salt by means of hydrochloric acid and ferric chloride.

3-Benzyl-2-(o-hydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium chloride.—*o*-Benzyl-acetoacetic ester (1 mol.) and salicylaldehyde (2 mols.) were mixed with dry ether and dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed as in the previous case. The highly coloured solution was allowed to stand and after two days the crystals that separated in dull red needles were filtered, washed with ether and dried. It crystallised from acetic acid as red needles, m.p. 129°. (Found: C, 77.11; H, 5.23. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2Cl$ requires C, 76.90; H, 5.07 per cent.)

3-Benzyl-2-(o-hydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium ferric chloride was obtained by adding ferric chloride to the pyrylium chloride dissolved in acetic acid. The ferric salt separated in red needles which, after crystallisation from acetic acid, had m.p. 194°. (Found: C, 53.81; H, 3.76. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2FeCl_4$ requires C, 53.63; H, 3.53 per cent.)

3-Benzyl-2-(o-hydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium perchlorate was prepared by adding perchloric acid to the pyrylium chloride solution of acetic acid. The red crystals were filtered, washed with ether and dried, m.p. 234°. (Found: C, 65.91; H, 4.45. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2Cl$ requires C, 65.66; H, 4.37 per cent.)

3-Benzyl-spiro-dibenzopyran was obtained by the decomposition of the above perchloric acid salt by the method already used. The crystals obtained by the evaporation of the ether were dissolved in benzene with the addition of animal charcoal, and from the solution on concentration the benzyl-spiro-dibenzopyran was obtained, m.p. 120°. (Found: C, 85.41; H, 5.64. $C_{22}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 85.17; H, 5.36 per cent.)

It is insoluble in petroleum ether and easily soluble in ether, benzene and alcohol. From the colourless solution the pyrylium compound is obtained as its ferric salt by hydrochloric acid and ferric chloride,

3-Methyl-2-(o-hydroxy-a-benzostyryl)-β-naphthopyrylium ferric chloride.—*β*-Naphthol-*a*-aldehyde (2 mols.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and to the solution *α*-methylacetoacetic ester (1 mol.) was added and the mixture, after saturation with hydrochloric acid gas with cooling, was kept overnight after which it was warmed on the water-bath for several hours. The deep coloured crystals, that separated from the solution of the pyrylium chloride on the addition of ferric chloride, were filtered, washed with acetic acid and finally with ether. (Found: C, 55·84; H, 3·56. $C_{26}H_{18}O_2FeCl_4$ requires C, 55·61; H, 3·88 per cent.)

3-Methyl-2-(o-hydroxy-a-benzostyryl)-β-naphthopyrylium perchlorate was prepared by adding perchloric acid to the solution of the pyrylium chloride. The crystals were filtered and crystallised from acetic acid; m.p. above 306°. (Found: C, 67·28; H, 4·27. $C_{26}H_{18}O_6Cl$ requires C, 67·43; H, 4·15 per cent.)

3-Methyl-spiro-2:2'-di(β-naphthyl-5:6-pyran-1:2) was obtained from the above ferric salt in the usual way using benzene in which it is soluble. The benzene solution was filtered from solids and boiled with animal charcoal; and from the filtrate on concentration colourless crystals were obtained, m.p. 200°. (Found: C, 86·33; H, 5·28. $C_{48}H_{36}O_8$ requires C, 86·15; H, 5·02 per cent.)

The *spiro*-dipyran is insoluble in ether and petroleum ether; readily soluble in hot benzene or toluene. The colourless solution, on boiling, assumes a blue-violet colour which disappears on cooling. From the colourless solution the pyrylium salt is again obtained as its ferric salt by adding hydrochloric acid and ferric chloride.

3-Benzyl-2-(o-hydroxy-a-benzostyryl)-β-naphthopyrylium ferric chloride was obtained from *β*-naphthol-*a*-aldehyde (2 mols.) and *α*-benzylacetoacetic ester (1 mol.) in glacial acetic acid solution which was saturated with hydrochloric acid gas with cooling. The mixture was then warmed on the water-bath for several hours. From the pyrylium chloride solution the ferric salt was precipitated by ferric chloride; the crystals were filtered, washed with acetic acid and ether, and dried. (Found: C, 94·12; H, 5·88. $C_{32}H_{28}O_2FeCl_4$ requires C, 94·85; H, 5·65 per cent.)

3-Benzyl-2-(o-hydroxy-a-benzostyryl)-β-naphthopyrylium perchlorate was prepared by adding perchloric acid to the acetic acid solution of the pyrylium chloride. The crystals were filtered, washed with ether and dried, m.p. 204°. (Found: C, 71·50; H, 4·22. $C_{32}H_{28}O_6Cl$ requires C, 71·28; H, 4·31 per cent.)

3-Benzyl-spiro-2:2'-di(β-naphtho-5:6-pyran-1:2).—The above ferric salt was decomposed as before. The benzene solution was boiled with animal charcoal, filtered and to the filtrate petroleum ether was added when the *spiro*-dinaphthopyran separated in colourless crystals, m.p. 205°. (Found: C, 87·88; H, 5·46. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 87·64; H, 5·78 per cent.)

2-Phenyl-3-methyl-benzopyrylium perchlorate.—(a) A mixture of *α*-methylbenzoyl-acetic ester (1 mol.), salicylaldehyde (1 mol.) and perchloric acid (1 mol.) was diluted with ether and the ethereal solution saturated with hydrochloric acid gas. The mixture was allowed to stand when the orange coloured crystals gradually separated. After two days these were filtered, washed with ether and crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 179°.

(b) Propiophenone (1 mol.), salicylaldehyde (1 mol.) and perchloric acid (1 mol.) were dissolved in ether and through the ethereal solution hydrochloric acid gas was passed. The orange needles that separated were crystallised from acetic acid; m.p. 179°. (Found: C, 59·68; H, 4·28. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2Cl$ requires C, 59·87; H, 4·08 per cent.)

A benzopyrylium salt has been obtained from salicylaldehyde and methylethylketone identical with that prepared from salicylaldehyde and *α*-methylacetoacetic ester. This part of the work will be described in a subsequent paper.

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